

Electrochemical behavior of some potential antibacterial hydrazones

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The electrochemical behavior of 2-(4'-sulfonamoyl)hydrazono-1,2-(2''-methyl)phenylaminobutane-1,3-diones was studied both at DME and GC electrodes. All arylhydrazones gave one four-electron, diffusion-controlled, irreversible wave/peak corresponding to the reduction of hydrazono group. On the basis of polarography, cyclic voltammetry, coulometry, end-product identification and spectral analysis, a redox mechanism has been suggested for the reduction of arylhydrazones at DME and GC electrodes.

The electrochemical behavior of hydrazones has been the subject of many investigations^{1,2}. However, only a few reports are available on the electroreduction of hydrazones at solid electrodes^{2,3}. Here we report electrochemical behavior of 2-(4'-sulfonamoyl)hydrazono-1,2-(2''-methyl)phenylaminobutane-1,3-diones to throw some light on the reduction of hydrazones.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic behavior : All the arylhydrazones (Table 1) exhibited single, well-defined, four-electron waves within the pH range 2.5–12.0 which can be attributed to the reduction of hydrazono group. The wave was found to be diffusion-controlled as evident by the linear plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} , and i_d vs concentration, passing through the origin. The

shift of half-wave potential towards more negative potential with increasing concentration of the depolarizer and the values of slope of the plot of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$ exceeded 59.2/n mV appreciably. Moreover, the numerical value of $(E_{3/4} - E_{1/4})$ was more than 56.4/n mV, indicating that the electrode process for the reduction of arylhydrazones is irreversible in nature. The values of αn and p were calculated as usual⁴.

$E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative values with increase in pH of the solution up to a pH around 8.0 and thereafter remained unchanged.

Cyclic voltammetry : Cyclic voltammograms of these compounds at GC electrode gave a single, well-defined four-electron peak at different scan rates (50–200 mV/s)

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics of 2-(4'-sulfonamoyl)hydrazono-1-(2''-methyl)phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione

pH = 4.6, conc. = 1.0×10^{-4} M

Sl. no.	R	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$ V	$D_0^{1/2}$ cm^2	j_d μA	αn	P	$I \times 10^{-2}$
1.		0.55	0.16	56.37	0.62	0.64	1.73	12.91
2.		0.58	0.16	63.58	0.50	0.59	1.35	10.46
3.		0.62	0.14	68.40	0.59	0.51	1.39	12.34
4.		0.56	0.16	62.96	0.51	0.58	1.57	10.60
5.		0.59	0.15	65.20	0.53	0.62	1.57	11.08
6.		0.48	0.16	55.26	0.54	0.86	2.32	11.29
7.		0.41	0.16	67.20	0.57	0.68	1.84	11.92

and concentrations ($0.5\text{--}2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$). The cathodic peak has been attributed to the reduction of hydrazono group of 2-(4'-sulfonamoyl)hydrazono-1-(2''-methyl)phenylaminobutane-1,3-diones. This peak has been found to be diffusion-controlled in nature by the linear dependence of peak current (i_p) on scan rate (v) and concentration of the depolarizer. The electrode process was found to be irreversible in nature by the dependence of E_p on the pH of solution and no anodic peak was observed in the reverse scan.

When the scan was reversed, a small anodic hump was observed at a far off positive potential. To study its relation with the reduction peak of the cathodic scan, cyclic voltammograms were first initiated in the positive direction and the small hump appeared in the anodic scan. This shows that this small hump is not due to the reduction product of the arylhydrazones. Hence, it was confirmed that the small hump in the anodic scan is due to the oxidation of the hydrazono group to $>C=O$ group. This oxidation peak was found to be pH-dependent as the E_p shifted towards more positive side with the increase in the pH. The irreversible nature of this anodic peak was confirmed by the linear dependence of the i_p on the concentration of the depolarizer.

Coulometry and controlled potential electrolysis : CPE of 2-(4'-sulfonamoyl)hydrazono-1-(2''-methyl)phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione at a potential slightly more negative than the reduction potential of hydrazono group was carried out and the reduction process consumed the electrons. The yellow colour of the starting material faded and the complete electrolysis was checked by recording the voltammograms at different time intervals. The two products were identified (TLC, IR) as sulfonamide (I) and (2''-methyl)phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione (II). ν_{\max} 3215 (NH_2), 2640 (C-H), 1690 cm^{-1} (C=O) and ammonia (detected by Nessler's reagent).

Redox mechanism : On the basis of the studies, the mechanism suggested for the reduction of arylhydrazones⁵ is presented in Scheme 1.

where $R' = CH_3$, $R'' = NHC_6H_4CH_3$

Scheme 1

The reduction mechanism involving cleavage of $-N-N-$ bond for arylhydrazones has also been proposed by other workers⁶.

A small anodic peak at faroff positive potential has been assigned to the two-electron oxidation of hydrazono group at GC electrode. The oxidation of the hydrazono group at this peak has been postulated as

This mechanism is supported by the work of other workers^{5,7,8}.

Effect of solvent composition : Effect of varying solvent composition on the polarographic characteristics of the compounds was studied by first recording polarograms in 30% DMF at pH 7.7. The percentage of solvent was then gradually increased from 30 to 70%. It was observed that $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more negative potential⁹ with increase in the percentage of solvent in the solution mixture. The i_d values went on decreasing. At very high percentage of organic solvent very ill-defined wave was obtained. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ to more negative potential with solvent percentage may be due to the rise in pH of solution¹⁰ which resulted in the increase in the dissociation constant of the protonated species. Furthermore, possibility for the shift of $E_{1/2}$ may also be due to the inhibition of the electrode process by solvent molecules absorbed¹¹ on the electrode. Another reason may be ascribed to a decrease in adsorbability, and hence surface concentration of the depolarizer with an increasing percentage of DMF in aqueous-organic mixture. Obviously decreased surface concentration¹² would retard the electrode process resulting in shift of $E_{1/2}$ and decrease in i_d .

Experimental

Various 2-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-1,3-(2''-methyl)phenylaminobutane-1,3-diones were synthesized by the method developed in this laboratory and purified by crystallization and their purity was checked by TLC.

Controlled potential electrolysis at DME and GC electrodes was done in a micro cell. For this purpose 2.0 ml of depolarizer, 4.0 ml of B.R. buffer, 3.0 ml of dimethylformamide and 1.0 ml of KCl was electrolyzed by the application of a potential slightly more negative than the peak potential for the respective peaks. From the decrease in current with time during electrolysis, the number of electrons transferred was calculated. Value of Q was read directly, and by the application of the following formula, number of electrons (n) were calculated :

Note

$$Q = nFN$$

$2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ solutions of all the compounds were prepared in purified dimethylformamide (A.R.). 1.0 M KCl (A.R.) was used as supporting electrolyte. Britton-Robinson buffers of different pH were prepared in double-distilled water using A.R. grade chemicals.

For preparing the solutions for polarographic and cyclic voltammetric studies. 1.0 ml of depolarizer, 2.0 ml of dimethyl formamide (to prevent precipitation), 1.0 ml of KCl and 6.0 ml of appropriate B.R. buffer were taken in the cell. The solution was deoxygenated¹³ by passing purified nitrogen gas for about 10 min and corrections for all residual currents were made in all cases by recording polarogram of the blank solution. Flow rate of mercury from the capillary was 2.1 mg/s and drop time 2.66 s at a height of 70 cm of mercury column.

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